

PREP4BLUE

METHODS AND TOOLS FOR MISSION OCEAN & WATERS

Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters

Deliverable D3.1

A readily accessible Inventory of Mission relevant CS initiatives in Europe to build awareness and provide online support for the community of practice.

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Executive Summary

Within the P4B project, the Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ) is leading task 3.2, which includes the establishment of a public database of all aquatic citizen science (CS) initiatives across the EU for the first time. Around 1000 aquatic citizen science initiatives have been identified in various topics and themes.

This inventory is freely available through an online database hosted on the PREP4BLUE project website and WaveLinks, accessible [HERE¹](#).

The CS database will provide online support for the Mission Ocean community of practice by:

- Allowing Mission-funded and Mission-relevant **research projects** to identify relevant CS initiatives for collaboration across the continent.
- Providing a mechanism for **local/municipal authorities** across Europe to identify CS initiatives that could become partners for data monitoring and analysis.
- Enabling **citizens** to join these projects when interested.
- Allowing **CS initiatives** to add their details to build awareness and increase the visibility of aquatic CS initiatives and their work in general.
- Laying the groundwork for establishing a future **European Aquatic Citizen Science Network**.

Acronyms & Abbreviations

Table 1. Table of abbreviations and acronyms used in Prep4Blue and the document.

Acronym / Abbreviation	Signification
P4B	PREP4BLUE
CS	Citizen Science
PE	Public Engagement
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association

¹ WaveLinks database: <https://wavelinks.eu/>

1 Introduction

The overarching objective of the PREP4BLUE project is to set the foundations for co-creating and co-implementing the research and innovation required to achieve the *Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030* (Mission Ocean). Central to this, is the development of tools and methods to increase the participation and engagement of the public in marine and riverine research, specifically in line with the citizen engagement target outcomes of Mission Ocean. The *Mission Ocean Implementation Plan* lists 10 such targets (European Commission, 2021, page 36), of which four explicitly mention Citizen Science (CS). The Mission's emphasis on CS is equally evident in the yearly Horizon Europe Mission Work Programmes. This deliverable – an online Inventory of Mission-relevant aquatic CS initiatives in Europe – has been designed to facilitate all Mission Activity that enables or is enabled by partnership with CS.

Access the Aquatic Citizen Science database [HERE](#)². After registering, select “Explore” to the left of the screen, then select “Citizen Science”.

CS is an ‘umbrella’ term that describes a variety of ways in which the public participates in science. The main characteristics are that: (1) citizens are actively involved in research, in partnership or collaboration with scientists or professionals; and (2) there is a genuine outcome, such as new scientific knowledge, conservation action or policy change. In our work, CS is defined according to the ten principles of CS from the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA)³. These are:

1. Citizen science projects actively involve citizens in scientific endeavor that generates new knowledge or understanding. Citizens may act as contributors, collaborators, or as project leader and have a meaningful role in the project.
2. Citizen science projects have a genuine science outcome. For example, answering a research question or informing conservation action, management decisions or environmental policy.
3. Both the professional scientists and the citizen scientists benefit from taking part. Benefits may include the publication of research outputs, learning opportunities, personal enjoyment, social benefits, satisfaction through contributing to scientific evidence e.g. to address local, national and international issues, and through that, the potential to influence policy.
4. Citizen scientists may, if they wish, participate in multiple stages of the scientific process. This may include developing the research question, designing the method, gathering and analysing data, and communicating the results.
5. Citizen scientists receive feedback from the project. For example, how their data are being used and what the research, policy or societal outcomes are.
6. Citizen science is considered a research approach like any other, with limitations and biases that should be considered and controlled for. However, unlike traditional research approaches, citizen science provides opportunity for greater public engagement and democratisation of science.
7. Citizen science project data and meta-data are made publicly available and where possible, results are published in an open access format. Data sharing may occur during or after the project, unless there are security or privacy concerns that prevent this.
8. Citizen scientists are acknowledged in project results and publications.

² Aquatic Citizen Science database: <https://wavelinks.eu/>

³ <https://www.ecsa.ngo/documents/>.

9. Citizen science programs are evaluated for their scientific output, data quality, participant experience and wider societal or policy impact.
10. The leaders of citizen science projects take into consideration legal and ethical issues surrounding copyright, intellectual property, data sharing agreements, confidentiality, attribution, and the environmental impact of any activities” (ECSA, 2015).

To support the further development and use of CS, the aquatic citizen science database was created to provide online support for the Mission Ocean community of practice by:

- Allowing Mission-funded and Mission-relevant **research projects** to identify relevant CS initiatives for collaboration across the continent.
- Providing a mechanism for **local/municipal authorities** across Europe to identify CS initiatives that could become partners for data monitoring and analysis.
- Enabling **citizens** to join these projects when interested.
- Allowing **CS initiatives** to add their details to build awareness and increase the visibility of aquatic CS initiatives and their work in general.
- Laying the groundwork for establishing a future **European Aquatic Citizen Science Network**.

2 Methods

2.1 Researched area and methods used

In this study, our classification of the researched marine regions was partly based on the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), executed by the European Union (Figure 1). In 2008, this law was adopted with the aim to better protect the marine environment across Europe (European Commission, 2008). This is an ambitious goal in which the contribution of citizen scientists to marine science could be essential.

Figure 1. Defined Marine Regions according to the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (Source: European Commission - 2015).

Starting from the MSFD (Figure 1), we added more specific marine and riverine areas to our classification. For this addition, we were inspired by the Atlas of the Sea, where river basins are mapped out showing their important connections to the seas defined in the MSFD (Figure 2).

Below, we included a table (Table 2) containing all the names of the seas and river basins included in our work. A more detailed map or description of the river basins or seas can be found on the website of the [European Atlas of the Sea](#).

Figure 2. Snapshot of the Atlas of the Sea website showcasing the different European sea basins.

Table 2. Overview of used names for researched seas and sea basins in Europe.

Number	Name	Number	Name
1	Norwegian Sea (NWS)	10	River basin to Norwegian Sea (RB > NWS)
2	Baltic Sea (BAL)	11	River basin to Baltic Sea (RB > BAL)
3	Greater North Sea, incl. English Channel and Kattegat (GNS)	12	River basin to Greater North Sea (RB > GNS)
4	Celtic Seas (CEL)	13	River basin to Celtic Seas (RB > CEL)
5	Biscay & Iberian Coast (BIB)	14	River basin to Biscay & Iberian Coast (RB > BIB)
6	Mediterranean Sea (MED)	15	River basin to Mediterranean Sea (RB > MED)
7	Black Sea (BLS)	16	River basin to Black Sea (RB > BLS)
8	Barents Sea (BAR)	17	River basin to Barents Sea (RB > BAR)
9	Oceanic NE Atlantic (NEA)		

The creation of our inventory, framed in the PREP4BLUE project, has its foundations rooted in earlier VLIZ-work. The study of van Hee *et al.* (2020) carried out similar research on a smaller scale, focusing on the North Sea area. As a first step, we revised the van Hee inventory and complemented the missing information whilst keeping a critical eye on the information already present in the database. As a second step, a team of four students dedicated their attention to an extensive Google search, consulting various information sources (e.g.: social media, citizen science databases, webpages etc.) and using specific search terms. The team focused on different sea and river areas, dividing the work and scanning the web for citizen science projects. Next to this ‘online’ investigation, organizations were directly contacted (via email or phone call) as well to check whether they were involved in particular CS projects or if they were aware of others.

With this on- and offline search, a database was compiled containing various parameters on each integrated CS project. In the table below (Table 3), the assessed variables can be found.

Table 3. Overview of the assessed variables in the developed aquatic citizen science inventory. An elaborate explanation of each variable can be found in appendix 1.

Variables				
ID number of project	Partners	Start year	Policy target	Activity location
Name of the project	Scope	End year	Data available on website	General aim
English project name	River/Sea basin	Frequency	Data type	# participants
Source/website link	Details area	Topic/discipline	Technology and support	Aim project
Organiser lead	Inclusive	Category	Technology: Specify	Overall description project
Country lead	Original language	Taxonomy Species	Level of participation	Contact details project lead
Type lead	Substantial material in English available	Invasive species	Co-creation	

Next to the Google search, a literature search on the Web of Science webpage was initiated. A set of keywords was compiled which linked to the following concepts/themes:

- (1) Citizen science/participatory science
- (2) Riverine/coastal environments
- (3) A specific European country

To combine these different search facets, Boolean operators “OR” and “AND” were utilized to make several sets of term combinations. An asterisk (*) was used to ensure the inclusion of variations on each of the terms in each query search.

In January 2023, three different countries (France, Austria, and the United Kingdom) were searched for citizen science projects using this method. However, a detailed and thorough check of the query results was impossible due to time constraints. Therefore, there was opted to not include the Web of Science query results into the citizen science project database. Undoubtedly, by making this choice, some citizen science projects will be missed and will not be integrated in the database. However, the landscape of citizen science projects is ever changing and perfectly capturing the entire field is not the aim of this database creation. Primarily, the focus is set on providing a general overview on which initiatives are present in the field across Europe and where opportunities in the citizen science scene can be found. The database can also be completed over time, so as its visibility increases, new or missing initiatives can add themselves.

2.2 What to consider as citizen science projects?

To work coherently, principles and definitions of citizen science used in the research report of van Hee *et al.* (2020) were adopted and only slightly altered regarding the broader objective of the PREP4BLUE citizen science database.

A base guideline, we used to help us in selecting the appropriate projects, was the ‘10 principles of citizen science’ listed by the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA - 2015). Adding to this, the following criteria were considered as well:

- (1) The selected projects must have an execution in waterbodies located on European territory (+UK) but can be lead globally or by a non-European country.
- (2) The projects must involve non-professionals in one or multiple stages of the scientific research process.
- (3) The project must have an authentic scientific outcome (e.g.: sightings, measurements, samples, pictures etc.).

Projects that have education or information transfer to citizens as the sole purpose are not included in the database.

3 Results

3.1 Online aquatic citizen science database.

The aquatic citizen science database is available as a link on the [P4B website](#). This link will lead you to the online database (WaveLinks) containing all identified European aquatic CS projects in D3.1 (Figure 3). It is possible to apply a filter on the database searching for: *Number of participants, Frequency, Scope, Activity location, Start year, End year, Policy task, Area, Category and Level of participation*. The filters will receive user feedback and improvements will be done based on that feedback. The possibility to add other projects will also be present (Figure 5). With this database we hope to support the creation of connections and synergies between citizen science projects, to provide inspiration and spark action among citizens.

Link to database: <https://wavelinks.eu/>

Figure 3. An overview page of the aquatic citizen science inventory on Wave Links. Here, users will be able to use the filters to search the database for specific projects linked to certain themes, topics, locations etc.

Figure 4. in the inventory site, there will be an overview option to see quick numbers and statistics of the database (e.g.: number of projects, projects per country etc.).

Citizen science
Fill the form to add a new citizen science initiative to the database

Search Overview Add new

Name *

Aim * Participants

Description

Start date * End date *

Topic Language

Country * Scope * Frequency Species

Leader * Add more leaders Partner 1 Add more partners

Data Area Lighthouse * Mission ocean objective

Contact name Contact email Contact phone number Website

Wave Links
Dashboard
Explore
Projects
Stakeholders
Engagement methods
Citizen science
Funding
Policy & legislation
Services
Networking
Monitoring
About us
Help
Contact us

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PREP4BLUE BLUE MISSION W4A BLUE MISSION BANDS

Figure 5. In the inventory there will be an option for the users to add a project that is not present in the database.

3.2 General results

Using the inventory of aquatic citizen science initiatives, a general increasing trend in the number of initiated citizen science projects (related to the ocean, seas or inland waters) is found (Figure 6). As a matter of fact, we see CS as a **rapidly emerging mode of research and innovation**, with an exponential growth in the number of projects particularly since 2010.

Figure 6. Abundance of aquatic citizen science projects over the years. Start date 1950 – end date 2023.

When taking a closer look at the explored **themes** in aquatic citizen science, a very strong bias towards biodiversity, species, habitat and pollution research is found (Figure 7). Opportunities for original and innovative projects lay in topics such as **fisheries, history, technology and aquaculture research**.

Figure 7. Pie chart of present themes in aquatic citizen science in Europe.

One of the Mission’s citizen engagement target outcomes is to “give European citizens the opportunity to engage in the preservation and restoration of oceans and waters through participative means, volunteering and citizen science” (European Commission, 2021, pg. 36). Promoting high levels of engagement through the entire arc of projects and activities (from planning, implementation, governance, to evaluation), is therefore desirable. However, when we look at the **level of involvement of citizens** in CS-projects (Figure 8), we see that there are few projects (13%) that requires a deep

participation of the citizens ('Participatory science' and 'Extreme citizen science'). This level of citizen science celebrates the full cooperation of non-professionals and scientists in every step of the research process. Here, co-creation is the baseline of the project and empowers citizens to take their own steps in research or problem-solving.

The majority of the projects (87%) opts for lower levels of citizen engagement ('Distributed intelligence' or 'Crowdsourcing'). At these levels, citizens participate in the project by collecting data (~ acting as sensors) or analysing already collected data (e.g.: counting the number of aquatic animals present in a picture). A specific skillset or knowledge is often not required at this citizen science level. More effort should therefore be made to increase participation levels in current CS initiatives, or Mission Ocean-funded projects could integrate participatory science or extreme citizen science into their project designs.

Figure 8. Overview of citizen engagement levels with linked project percentage.

The inventory shows that many aquatic CS projects in Europe are **coordinated by** scientific institutions or NGOs, much less by governments or the private industry (Figure 9). There is room for **expansion towards sectors that are less familiar with CS** since this can bring various new perspectives into the CS narrative.

Figure 9. Pie chart on project leads in aquatic citizen science initiatives in Europe.

When focusing on Mission Objective 3 – Make the Blue Ecoomy Carbon Neutral and Circular – only 8% of the projects have citizen science in their project set-up. Therefore, the possibility for citizens to engage in projects involved in decarbonization is rather low currently. Decarbonization projects often encompass topics such as species (37%), habitat (23%) and abiotic (10%) research. Again, future Mission funding calls and Mission-funded projects could focus on integrating citizen science into these research topics. This is particularly important in the Baltic and North Sea Lighthouse Basin, which takes Objective 3 as its focus.

Looking at the different sea and river basins, it shows a nice distribution (Figure 10). However, opportunities lie in the river basins near the Barents Sea and the Black Sea. A peak in aquatic citizen science projects is located in the Greater North Sea (incl. the English Channel and Kattegat).

Figure 10. Overview of project distribution over the various sea and river basins (Full names of areas can be found in Table 2).

4 Conclusions - Recommendations

A key pillar of Mission Ocean is to develop tools and methods to increase the participation of the public in aquatic research and in the co-management of their aquatic resources. To foster deeper and more interactive engagement of citizens with Mission Ocean, the incorporation of citizens into aquatic scientific projects presents a promising path. Of the 10 citizen engagement target outcomes listed in the Mission Ocean Implementation Plan, (European Commission, 2021, page 36), four explicitly mention citizen science (CS). The CS approach creates a sense of closeness and connection to aquatic ecosystems and environments, nurturing a shared commitment to their preservation.

The aquatic citizen science database created in this task identifies the gaps, opportunities and potential paths for collaboration in the field of aquatic citizen science. As its visibility grows and its use increases alongside the number of projects listed, it sets the foundation for the further integration of CS into formal monitoring and data collecting arrangements across the continent. By implementing the recommendations of the created report in starting or upscaling CS initiatives, CS can become a key enabler for monitoring the progress of Mission Ocean towards its objectives, and achieving Mission Ocean's citizen engagement target outcomes.

Below, we summarise some of the most promising actions Europe and Mission Ocean can undertake to support the momentum of the rising CS tendency in starting initiatives, projects and science in general.

Action 1: Support innovative and creative project topics in aquatic CS.

By creating the inventory, general trends could be defined in the setup of European aquatic CS projects. Since 2010, CS has exponentially infiltrated the aquatic research and innovation world. Especially in projects focusing on biodiversity, species and pollution (mainly plastic) research, the citizen science approach has found its way into various research projects. However, themes such as aquaculture, fisheries, aquatic technology, archaeology, remain relatively underexplored and hold further potential to unravel new perspectives and insights in our ocean and waters. Another remarkable finding shows us that Mission Ocean's Objective 3 – Creating a carbon neutral and circular Blue Economy – is generally overlooked when setting up projects with a citizen science component. When checking for decarbonization projects, only 8% of projects can be linked to this topic, in which the Blue Economy is severely underrepresented. While this objective is extremely important in working towards a global sustainable climate, there is still an open road to set up new and innovative projects (with citizens) to achieve this ambitious goal. Having citizens participate in climate related projects, making them part of the research and possible solutions, might encourage them to act more and ultimately support climate measures taken by governmental bodies. Here, we wish to encourage projects to implement our recommendations and good practices to foster creativity and innovation in these underrepresented subjects to fill in the knowledge gaps. Mission Ocean can aid this process by specifically creating calls that further encourage the use of citizen produced data to explore decarbonization and circular blue economy topics.

Action 2: Let the citizen be the starting point.

One of the Mission's citizen engagement target outcomes is to "give European citizens the opportunity to engage in the preservation and restoration of oceans and waters through participative means, volunteering and citizen science" (European Commission, 2021, pg. 36).

Promoting high levels of engagement through the entire arc of projects and activities (from planning, implementation, governance, to evaluation), is therefore desirable. However, the level of engagement in European aquatic citizen science initiatives is rather low. In 87% of the projects, there is opted for crowdsourcing or distributed intelligence. While these types of engagement are valuable and need continuation, there is a scope for growth towards more interactive forms of citizen science. Only 13% of the projects mapped out, apply higher engagement levels creating more participation and involvement of citizens. Of this 13%, there is only 1% of the projects that use an extreme citizen science approach and where co-design/co-creation form the project's core.

Opportunities lie in higher forms of citizen engagement since these induce possible behavioural change in society towards more sustainable and healthy aquatic ecosystems. Note that lower forms of engagement are still crucial in gathering much needed data and not all projects should strive to have extreme citizen science in their methodology. Striking a balance between various engagement levels, where different CS projects can support each other, is the way forward.

Action 3: Involve the 'unusual' suspects.

Next to this, many aquatic CS projects in Europe are coordinated by scientific institutions or NGOs, much less by governments, policy actors or the private industry. Setting up projects in these sectors or in specific fields can create new perspectives on our ocean and waters. Another route worth exploring is the inclusion of water(sports) enthusiasts (e.g.: divers, fishers, beach guards, boaters, surfers etc.). This target group is often very passionate about the ocean or inland waters and could be open to participate in aquatic CS projects. However, there are only a limited number of projects that specifically include this group. Diversifying funding opportunities (e.g.: specific calls) for 'atypical' project initiators and involving more 'unusual' sectors or groups in citizen science can bridge the existing involvement gap and include all representatives of the quadruple-helix model. Teaming up with the European Solidarity Corps (another of the Mission's citizen engagement target outcomes) as a pool of citizen scientists is another underexplored option with high potential.

Note that these suggestions to include 'unusual' suspects more into aquatic CS, also applies for social inclusion. Citizen science is (unwillingly) biased if no effort is made to include all societal layers and give everyone the opportunity to participate in citizen science. No one should be left behind.

Action 4: Connect our ocean and inland waters.

A last point we would like to touch upon is the opportunity to create more projects that link the inland waters to the ocean. Only very few projects aim to tackle occurring problems in rivers (and inland waters) and in the ocean simultaneously. To achieve a clean and healthy ocean, we need to start focusing on the importance of having clean and healthy rivers and inland waters, that are all interconnected to each other and to the ocean, as well. Dedicated calls, targeting this connection and therefore these inland waters can be a step in the right direction.

The dedication and enthusiasm of citizen science project initiators, combined with the valuable insights collected or brought up by citizen scientists, have the potential to drive meaningful change and ensure the conservation and restoration of our aquatic environments for generations to come. An essential tool in keeping the CS momentum vivid, is the sharing of knowledge and experiences via

trainings, workshops or webinars. Exchanging practical and hands-on knowledge eliminates gatekeeping and enables new (or running) CS projects to thrive. As can be seen from the P4B webinar series on various citizen engagement topics, there is a high interest in interactive platforms that give projects the opportunity to learn and ask practical questions. We hope that the P4B database, together with the recommendations report on aquatic CS can be a starting point for many innovative and creative European projects in the future. Supported by the Mission Ocean and the European Commission, we hope that many aquatic citizen science journeys, may ripple out, and make a lasting impact on our shared waters.

5 Bibliography

ECSA. (2015). *'Ten principles of Citizen Science.'* The European Citizen Science Association. Last accessed 23 October 2023. <https://www.ecsa.ngo/documents/>

European Atlas of the Seas. (n.d.).

https://ec.europa.eu/maritimeaffairs/atlas/maritime_atlas/#lang=EN;p=w;bkgd=5;theme=11:0.9;c=1251146.3995731715,7243552.005087748;z=4.

European Commission. (2008). *Marine environment*.

https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/marine-environment_en.

European Commission. (2015). *Delineation of the MSFD Article 4 marine regions and subregions*.

https://circabc.europa.eu/sd/a/e0d8d790-b773-41c8-b88b-868be93455af/MSFD%20Marine%20regions%20and%20subregions_metadata_20150714.pdf.

European Commission. (2021). *Restore Our Oceans and Waters: Implementation Plan*.

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/restore-our-ocean-and-waters_en#documents. Last accessed 1 November 2023.

van Hee, F.M., Seldenrath, A., Seys, J. (2020). Policy Informing Brief: Marine Citizen Science in the North Sea area - and what policy makers can learn from it. VLIZ Beleidsinformerende nota's BIN 2020_007. Oostende, 35 pp.

6 Appendix 1

Variable	Explanation
ID number	Number given to classified project to keep count of project amount.
Name project	Name of the classified aquatic citizen science project.
English project name	The English translation of the project's name.
Source/website link	The website or link to the project.
Organiser lead	The name of the project's organization.
Country lead	The leading country in which the project was founded.
Type lead	The type of organization/institution/group that leads the project. Possible options were: community or partnership/government or policy/industry or private sector/ museum or exposition/NGO or non-profit or charity/person or individual/ research institute/science center/university or college.
Partners	If partners were involved yes or no, specification options were possible for the categories mentioned in the 'type lead' variable.
Scope project	The geographical scope of the project can be defined, options were: Locally, Regionally, Nationally, European or Globally. Further specification was possible for the seas and sea basins mentioned in table A
River/Sea basin	The river or sea basin in which the project is located.
Details area	Further specific details could be given about the researched area (e.g.: Catalan coast) and which type of water was researched (e.g.: sea, coastal, estuary, other inland waters, inland countryside, urban environment).
Specific to water?	Is the project specific to water?
Inclusive?	Does the project invest specifically in inclusivity?
Original language(s)	In which language was the project set up?
Substantial info in English available	Is there information on the project to find in English?
Start year	Start year of the project.
End year	End year of the project.

Variable	Explanation
Frequency	The frequency of the citizen science activities can be specified by: one time event/once a year/multiple times a year/continuously.
Topic/discipline (max. 5 words)	General topic of the project.
Category	Categorisation of the project by general themes: Abiotic/All/Aquaculture/Archeology/Biodiversity/Fisheries/Habitat (biodiversity+species)/History/Pollution/Species(group)/Technology.
Taxonomy species(group)	When project researched a certain species, here specifications on the species could be filled in.
Policy target	Project link to specific policy target.
Invasive species	Is the project dealing with invasive species?
Data available on website	Is data freely available on the project's website?
Data type	Which data type is collected in the project: Sightings, imagery, collection, systematic observations, measurements.
Technology & Support	Is technology used in the project and by who is it provided (participant or project).
Technology: Specify	Which specific piece of technology is used?
Level of participation	Which participation level is used in the project: Crowdsourcing/Distributed intelligence/Participatory science/Extreme citizen science.
Co-creation with citizens?	Is co-creation by citizens included in the project?
Activity location	Does the project take place outdoors/indoors with specification option.
General aim	Which endgoal does the data serve: Descriptive, Composite, Performance
# participants	Indicate the range of participants in the project: < 100, 100 – 1000, < 1000, NA.
Aim project	Describe the endgoal of the project.
Short overall description project	Shortly describe the overall project flow and mechanisms.
Contact details	Name/email/phone number of main project coordinator.